

CREATING TIME: LONG TERM ON THE SHORT TERM

REBECCA E. NORDQUIST

PUBLISHED ON EDUBLOGS ON JANUARY 23, 2025

<https://rebeccanordquist.edublogs.org/2025/01/23/creating-time-long-term-on-the-short-term/>

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Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14726373

“Life is long if you know how to use it.” — Seneca

I've recently been introduced to applied philosophy, especially in relation to education- specifically the book *Applied Philosophy for Health Professions Education* (Brown et al., 2022). I have a weakness for philosophy books but in all honesty, reading philosophy for me is very slow going. Its more about a phrase

or sentence here or there that sticks with me, and gets me thinking. So reading philosophy in the context of education, while I enjoy it and it makes me think, in reality: who has time for this kind of slow going? I put down the chapter I was working through and got back to prep work for the day of teaching.

This time of year is a busy one, with several courses running at the same time, and “the rest” of work that continues at full speed in the meantime. During a meeting this week with my tutor students, we discussed professional development and thinking about the long term. What kind of veterinarian do you want to be? What personal development goals do you want to set for the medium-term, largely based on Biesta’s socialization and subjectification (Biesta, 2020).

As we were working on this, and discussing what personal development means, it became clear the students were not all “there”; they were distracted. There are several big finals in the next week; that is where all of their thoughts were. When I asked them about it, responses were variations of “I would be really much more open to this if it was planned in a different week!”

I understand the dilemma. But... learning to keep the long term in mind while working toward the short-term, is also part of professionalization. We talked about how as a professional, work is never “done”. My job is never “done”; there is always something left to work on. Learning to carve out time for reflection and long-term planning – and protect that time even in “crunch” time – is an essential skill for a happy professional life. These are things they are going to face on graduation, and better to learn now than become one of the veterinarian burn-out statistics.

After getting off of my soap box, I thought back to my philosophy reading.... And sheepishly blocked off time on my busy calendar to read, and a day this weekend for photography. Because personal development, long-term development goals, *and* making time for non-work, are important for all of us. Life is long if you know how to use it.

Biesta, G. (2020). Risking Ourselves in Education: Qualification, Socialization, and Subjectification Revisited. *Educational Theory*, 70(1), 89–104.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/edth.12411>

Brown, M. E. L., Veen, M., & Finn, G. M. (2022). *Applied philosophy for health professions education: A journey towards mutual understanding* (1–1 online resource (xviii, 380 pages) : illustrations). Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-1512-3>

Seneca, L. A., & Costa, C. D. N. (1997). *On the shortness of life*. Penguin Books.